

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GRAPHIC COMPETENCE OF ENGINEERING COMPUTER GRAPHICS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *It is necessary to use innovations on a large scale in higher education institutions specializing in the training of highly qualified personnel. As a result of the popularization of this process, higher education institutions, in connection with science, production and the market, become important for the training of qualified specialists.*

Keywords: *“Competencies”, “graphic digital technology”, “graphic competence”, “graphic-drawing”, “project design”, “design activity”, “graphic competence”.*

In the context of deepening processes of globalization and integration in the world, the need to improve the professional graphic competence of the technological education teacher through the development of digital technology compensations is increasing. That is why it is urgent to conduct scientific research on the use of digital technologies, the development of skills to work effectively with digital technology, and the development of professional graphic competence, based on the norms and international standards established in the strategic projects of UNESCO "Structural structure of teachers' digital technology competence", "Qualified teachers for all education". is gaining importance.

Effective use of skills and qualifications (competencies) based on knowledge of graphic knowledge, functional and constructive uniqueness of objects in the development of professional graphic competence of teachers in world practice, graphic professional orientation and activity experience, creation of an environment of free creativity in graphic digital technology, successful professional and pedagogical activity, its importance and attitude to certain technological issues, the system of corrective exercises aimed at preventing mistakes made by the teacher are of particular importance. In this regard, it is necessary to develop a scientifically based system of development of professional graphic competence in the process of formation of design, manufacturing, technological and communicative competences in state educational standards, qualification requirements, training programs prepared by teachers in the field of engineering computer graphics education in higher educational institutions.

General professional (knowledge and skills, abilities that determine the professional mobility of future specialists) and non-professional professional

The development of competence includes the development of the ability to get ideas about the variety of complex and unpredictable production situations, the consequences of professional activity and to take responsibility for them. Maturity is recognized as the leading criterion for preparing graduates of modern technological education to work in unstable, rapidly changing conditions of professional activity and social life.

Competence is defined as the ability to work effectively, the ability to achieve results, and the ability to effectively solve problems. It defines the availability of knowledge, skills, education as a person's readiness and ability to use theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve various problems, contribute to personal self-awareness, tasks in the world as a way to find a student who takes his place. Competence is a real, formable personal quality based on intellectual

and personal-conditional social characteristics of a person. For engineering computer graphics, such important features of competence are noted as the effective use of skills; ability to do good work; is the level of formation of a complex of knowledge, skills, property, and experience from a specialist that ensures the implementation of professional activity. The ability to mobilize these knowledge, skills and experiences in a specific socio-professional situation characterizes the tasks of a professional successful person.

The theoretical analysis allowed us to distinguish graphic competence as a necessary part of professional competence, which describes the level of preparation of future teachers for professional activities in modern production conditions.

To determine the essence of the concept of "graphic competence", we created a logical line to describe the main concepts: graphic-drawing - project - design - design activity - graphic competence. In modern education, the project method is one of the most effective methods of implementing the mechanism of formation of professional culture in the educational process, and it is manifested in the ability to develop important professional personal characteristics of the future specialist by combining the educational process with science and production. The basis of the educational process in the project activity is not only the acquisition of knowledge, but also the methods of self-improvement, the development of the creative potential of students, and the improvement of the quality of work.

Within the framework of one project, the qualities of future specialists, professionally important components of professional culture, interact with the following principles: educational, professional and experimental design activities (improvement of the model of professional training, establishing contact with professional activities), professional training and self-awareness of students creativity (development of creative potential), interdisciplinarity (interdependence of different fields of knowledge, coherence of teaching methods and forms), environmental friendliness during the formation of skills.

The teacher of engineering computer graphics should be prepared to organize and teach project activities of students, because the method of projects is one of the foundations of the field of education "Engineering computer graphics". Therefore, drawing should be used in educational design-constructive activities. In order to integrate the design-constructive activity of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions with the science of mechanical engineering drawing, it is necessary to develop their creativity, constructive-technical, ideas, graphic and textual components of educational projects and prepare materials for their protection.

The model of the system of formation and development of graphic competence of engineering computer graphics students is considered on the basis of a person-oriented, modular-competency, subject integration and practical activity approach in the organization of the methodical process.

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